

Materials and Methods and Research Results and Discussion

Fayzullayev Sarvar Ibrohim ugli
Teacher of Tashkent Medical academy

Abstract. *This article provides information on the importance of the English language and its role in the world. This article also explains the importance of English in the field of medicine, first of all, along with the stages of becoming a doctor, and through many methods on how to learn English quickly and easily in medical institutions.*

Keywords: *Results, the USA and the UK knowledge, questions and answers, develop the ability, repeat those words, memory, speech and etc.*

Introduction In this work, meeting the demands of the theme, comparative-historical classification methods are used. Scientific source materials form its subject. Globalization and accelerated exchange of information require knowledge of the language of international communication and, in particular, its special features and the use of terminology in the medical professions. Consequently, it becomes urgently necessary to acquire reading skills and a good understanding of the medical literature in the English language for progressing to the level required for communication with colleagues from the USA, the UK, Australia, Israel and other countries known for their significant achievements in the development of medicine. Why should a doctor know English? First of all, it may seem that the doctor's knowledge of English is not the key aspect in professional growth. In fact, if you aim at the constant improvement of skills and want to work in a prestigious clinic, and even more so, to cooperate with your foreign colleagues, you must know English. Knowing English, you can freely read foreign medical journals, most of the modern books on medicine; are acquainted with publications in the English language on medical websites. In addition, of course, in terms of volume and relevance, such information significantly compares favorably with the information available in Russian or Kazakh. Knowledge of English allows the doctor to have an appointment with foreign patients in private clinics. Probably, if you work in a small clinic of a small town, only your compatriots will seek your medical advice. But, for example, in a private clinic of the capital city, cooperating with insurance companies, you can have foreign patients. If you plan to work or undertake an internship abroad, you cannot do it without knowledge of the English language.

Following, there are some methods, how learn English language fast and easily. In the early stages, the emphasis is on reading aloud. Reading texts are also simpler and easier to read. However, it should be noted that although the work in the early stages is mainly focused on the development of oral skills, it does not solve the problem of developing oral communication in English. She is only in the process of preparing for a real oral presentation. In addition, reading words beautifully and fluently will increase a student's love of learning the language. In addition, students will be introduced to The Present indefinite Tense, The Past indefinite Tense, The Future indefinite Tense is required to be familiar with verb tenses and to be able to use verb forms vividly in these tenses. Students learn that nouns are used in the singular and plural, that suffixes are added to the third person singular form of a verb in the present indefinite tense, and that interrogative, negative, and imperative forms of sentences are also introduced at an early stage. during the study period. In the middle stage of teaching English, the focus should be on using techniques that help to increase

thinking, speaking, and initiative in reading and understanding larger texts. Students will be given homework assignments. Exercises to check comprehension of the text are given and can be expressed as follows: Answer the question on the text Samarkand: Why Samarkand is called like this? Where is the ancient center of the city? How many people live there? Question-answer exercises are used to strengthen the student's speech, improve memory, and repeat the results. New words from the text are memorized. Questions and answers develop the ability to repeat those words in memory and to use them in speech. In addition, a variety of games in the classroom will increase the student's interest in learning the language and increase the speed of learning. In the Hot Ball game, students form a circle and say one of the new words to each other on the ball. Participants do not repeat each other's words, are expelled from the game if they repeat or stop speaking. That's the way to play. In the middle stage, grammar is taught in more depth than in the first stage, and students are given knowledge, exercises and tests based on the rules of grammar. Computer and phone language learning programs are also great for elementary and middle school language learning. Examples include Talk (English speaking practice), Daily English, Learn English (English master), How to speak real English. These programs are designed to include all sections of reading, listening, and testing. Recording new words on a phone dictaphone is another great way to repeat in your spare time. Also, showing more English subtitles and cartoons is an effective way to teach the language. At the senior level, independent work plays a special role, especially in a foreign language. The requirements for this course are different from those of the previous stages. The lesson is no longer based on oral speech, because at this stage most of the language material is studied passively (receptively). That is, reading comprehension plays a key role. The texts are also large in size and the language material is complex. Reading, speaking, listening exercises are held regularly. When organizing a lesson, a separate day is set for Reading, a separate day for Speaking, and a separate day for Listening. Homework is also more complex than previous steps. Speaking lessons include a 2-minute talk with a topic. Alternatively, text cards will be distributed to students. Each student gives their opinion on the topic on the card of their choice. The speech requires the use of previous combinations, phrases, introductions, new words, synonyms. If you want to learn a foreign language quickly and with quality, you should try to follow simple tips while reading. They are designed to reduce the impact of age-related changes in your brain, as well as help make the whole process as easy and invisible as children. Repeat from time to time This method allows you to better memorize new words and concepts. This is because you need to repeat the studied material at regular intervals, and the smaller these intervals. For example, if you are learning new words, you should repeat them several times during a lesson, then the next day. Then reinforce the material after a few more days and finally after a week. The process looks like this in a rough graph: One of the programs that has been used successfully using this approach. The program can track which words you have learned and remind you to repeat them after a certain amount of time. At the same time, new lessons are built using learned material, so the knowledge you gain is solidly reinforced. Learn the language before going to bed To learn a new language, you basically need to remember a large amount of information. Yes, it is advisable to understand their application to grammatical rules, but basically you will need to memorize new words along with examples. To get good memorization, don't miss the opportunity to repeat the material again before bed. Research by American scientists has shown that memorization before bed is much stronger than during daytime classes. Learn content, not just language Teachers with extensive experience are well aware that learning a foreign language abstractly is much more difficult than mastering any interesting material. This is also confirmed by scientists. For example, in a recent experiment, one group of participants learned French in the usual way, while another taught one of the core subjects in French. As a result, the second group made significant progress in listening and translating. We are all always busy and it is not easy to make time for full-time workouts. Therefore, many people limit themselves to 2-3 hours per week, which is specially allocated for a foreign language. However, it is better to do the workout with time, but every day. Our brains do not have a large buffer of random access memory. If we try to gather the maximum amount of data in an hour, the wave will appear quickly. There are more benefits, but from time to time. Special things that allow you to train in any of your free time are very suitable for this.

Therefore, be sure to complement your activities by consuming content that interests you in the target language. This includes listening to podcasts, watching movies, reading books and so on.

THE LIST OF USED REFERENCES

1. TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN MEDICAL INSTITUTES Rakhmatova Sunbula, Djabbarova Sitora Bakhodurovna, Nuraliyeva Ozoda Norboyevna, Sherbekova Yulduz Zokir kizi, Matyakubova Shakhnoza Ilkhombekovna - Journal of Positive School Psychology <http://journalppw.com> 2022, Vol. 6, No. 5, 1605 – 1613.
2. Developing professional communicative competence of medical students in a foreign language Akhmedova Matluba Ibragimjonovna - Eurasian Scientific Herald Volume 15, December, 2022
3. Fayzullaev, S. (2023). Improving the methodology of teaching foreign languages based on the competence approach in the higher medical education system. *Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке*, 1(9), 697-700.
4. Sarvar, F. (2023). OLIY TA'LIM TIZIMIDA TA'LIM METODLARINING QO'LLANILISHI.
5. Israilova, I., Gulfura, T., Patima, T., Gulbakhor, M., & Sarvar, F. (2021). Medical english learning through authentic movies: extra-linguistic factors contributing to the study of medical terminology. *Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities*, 1(1.5 Pedagogical sciences).
6. Fayzullayev, S. (2023). MECHANISM OF INTEGRATED TEACHING OF SPEECH COMPETENCE IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES IN MEDICINE.
7. Sarvar, F. (2022). Mechanism of integrated teaching of speech competence in Uzbek and English languages in medicine Tashkent Medical Academy.
8. Sarvar, F. (2023). HISTORY OF BRITISH VS. AMERICAN ENGLISH. *Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке*, 2(14), 49-53.
9. Fayzullayev, S. I. FOR IMPROVING MEDICAL STUDENTS'ENGLISH SKILLS. *World of Scientific news in Science*, 2(6), 16-23.
10. Fayzullayev, S. I. (2024). WAYS OF EFFECTIVE USE OF EDUCATIONAL METHODS AND ITS EFFECTIVENESS. *PEDAGOGIKA, PSIXOLOGIYA VA IJTIMOIIY TADQIQOTLAR| JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGY, PSYCHOLOGY AND SOCIAL RESEARCH*, 3(4), 185-189.
11. Fayzullayev, S. (2022). Chet tillariga ixtisoslashmagan oliy ta'lim muassasalarida chet tili o'qitishning maqsadi.
12. Fayzullayev, S. (2022). Methods to improve english in medical institutions. Collection of materials international scientific and practical conference" Modern scientific research in medicine: current issues, achievements and innovations".